

The Psychological Impact of Climate Change Anxiety: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

Introduction: Climate change is a significant source of psychological distress, causing eco-anxiety, depression, and stress, especially in at-risk groups such as young people and families. This systematic review explores the prevalence, and psychological impact, of climate change anxiety (CCA), considering different age groups and geographic regions.

Methods: Studies were identified from an online search of PubMed, Web of Science, Cochrane Library, and Embase databases without any search time range. This review has been registered on Open OSF.

Results: Recent research shows that CCA has a major effect on mental health in different groups. Online therapy for cognitive behavioral therapy is promising for reducing climate-related distress, as eco-anxiety is associated with higher psychological distress and changed behavior, particularly in young people and professionals. Techniques like psycho-educational methods and nature-connectedness strategies play a vital role in reducing these impacts and enhancing mental health.

Conclusions: CCA affects mental health in various ways, impacting people of all ages and in different locations. Efficient strategies can relieve stress and promote eco-friendly behavior, and a deep bond with the natural world could also aid in lessening feelings of worry.

Keywords: Climate Change Anxiety; Climate Change Impacts; Climate Distress; Eco-anxiety; Environmental Psychology; Mental Health; Psychological Impact; Young People.

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INTRODUCTION

Climate change is a profound psychological stressor, having a determining effect on physical and mental health in myriad ways. Its repercussions are not limited to environmental concerns, creating psychological ramifications in the shape of eco-anxiety, a continuous fear of the world's future. This pathological form of anxiety can lead to a cycle of depression, stress, and hopelessness, particularly within vulnerable sectors of society, for example, young adults and families with children [1, 2]. The dislocation of familiar terrains produced by climate change exacerbates these emotions, leaving a pervasive sadness and a visceral sense of loss [3].

Therefore, climate anxiety has emerged as a developing problem regarding mental health as current or projected environmental change plays a factor in its availability. Eco-anxiety stems from deep, chronic concern for the fate of the planet because of climate change. Although climate change is evident in fears about sea levels and brush fires, it also presents a diverse array of psychological symptoms that can seep into daily life. Evidence suggests an increase in climate change anxiety (CCA) among global populations, especially in areas hardest hit by climate change. Studies show that more than half of youths in such areas report exposure to unmanageable anxiety about the long-term consequences of the changes in the environment to which they are accustomed [4,5].

This is especially true for women and others who are closely connected to nature or who live in climate-vulnerable regions [6]. Psychological symptoms of CCA include elevated stress and emotional distress [6] and, in some cases, avoidant behaviors, such as avoiding topics of conversation around climate change due to feelings of being overwhelmed [7]. On the other hand, some may get heavily involved in environmental activism as a means of coping but at the risk of burnout without the appropriate balance of self-care [8–12].

Common physical manifestations of CCA are tension, sleep disturbances, and fatigue [13]. The ongoing concern with climate change can compound feelings of inadequacy, helplessness, and sadness [14,15]. Individuals with climate anxiety, for example, might show greater levels of generalized anxiety (i.e., panic attacks or phobias related to environmental catastrophes) and depressive symptoms like low mood or loss of interest in activities [16]. These traits may be defined as correlational psychopathologic features, with a significant impact on daily life. Specific vulnerability factors to frictions related to disorders that lead to such disastrous outcomes may refer to pre-existing or predisposed psychological profiles, including personality traits such as high levels of anxiety (i.e., generalized anxiety disorder, obsessive-compulsive disorder), extreme sensitivity, degree of empathy, and environmental awareness, factors that make individuals more vulnerable to, and concerned by, environmental hazards [17].

Furthermore, traumatic events associated with major extreme weather events can significantly increase susceptibility to climate change anxiety [18]. The psychopathology underlines the necessity of evaluating CCA to have a clearer understanding of its implications in mental health as well as to determine those who require assistance. Correct assessment is vital in tailoring interventions, allowing mental health professionals to help with the presenting problems. These include the Climate Change Anxiety Scale (CCAS), the Eco-Anxiety Questionnaire (EAQ), the Environmental Distress Scale (EDS), the Climate Change and Mental Health Questionnaire (CCMHQ), and the Climate Change Worry Scale (CCWS) [19–23]. These tools are described in Table 1.

In addition, solving CCA needs a comprehensive approach that combines psychological, social, and behavioral approaches. Educating individuals by providing evidence-based, correct, relevant, and accessible information regarding climate change can empower them and diminish helplessness through the provision of actionable steps and solutions [24,25]. Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) can help people overcome irrational or exaggerated thoughts about climate change to encourage a more rational perspective. Adding climate and ecological destruction concerns to CBT makes it possible to tailor treatments more closely to individual fears and concerns [26,27]. Activism on environmental issues is also a useful way for handling anxiety about climate change. Participation in community activities or green behaviors creates a sense of empowerment in individuals. However, working towards activism and personal well-being to not only decrease burnout and remain consistently involved is necessary [28–30].

The social support network, including friends, therapists, and support groups, plays an important role in exchanging coping strategies and developing collective resilience [31–33]. Education and training can help people dealing with the psychological consequences of climate change. Meditation, relaxation and stress management techniques, and mindfulness exercises can be beneficial in making anxiety more manageable. These interventions are designed to protect mental well-being against the impacts of transformation in a changing environment by addressing both the emotional and specific aspects of CCA [34,35]. CCA varies across different-aged and geographically distinct populations and is therefore a continuum of responses to environmental stress. In youth and adolescence, however, climate anxiety is usually future-oriented; the distress and helplessness that come in the wake of it tend to be pronounced. Most of the youth are angry toward political leaders, perceiving inaction that is perceived as increasing hopelessness and urgency of action [36,37]. In contrast, older populations may worry about how climate change will impact their current circumstances and the legacy they will leave for future generations.

This group is often confronted with a lack of familiar environments and concerns about psychological and physical security [38,39]. The geographic location plays a decisive role in the occurrence of CCA as well. In regions directly affected by extreme weather events, rising sea levels, or temperature changes, anxiety is heightened due to immediate and tangible threats to homes and livelihoods [40]. Conversely, the same is not true for those who do not live directly within the path of devastation, and for them, anxiety may take on a more conceptual profile as formed by international media reports rather than more visceral encounters [41]. More socially and economically, CCA expression also relies on environmental conditions, with low-income neighborhoods constantly facing disproportionate emotional burdens due to limited resources, whereas wealthy areas could benefit from increased access to supportive networks [42,43]. The elements related to CCA are outlined in Figure 1. Understanding this phenomenon is critical for developing tailored interventions and support mechanisms and, consequently, for promoting integrated mental health and environmental strategies [44,45].

Therefore, this systematic review aims to explore the prevalence and psychological impact of CCA across different age groups and geographic regions.

Table 1. A summary of instruments to measure the levels of dysfunction in psychological climate change.

Psychological Climate Change Tests	Description
Climate Change Anxiety Scale (CCAS)	The CCAS was designed as a way to measure how much anxiety people are feeling about climate change. It consists of 12 items that assess various components of eco-anxiety, including emotional distress, worries about future environmental consequences, and behavior change. Respondents rate their feelings and concerns about climate change on a 5-point Likert scale. The CCAS is used to assess the severity of climate-related distress and to identify individuals who may need specialized mental health support. It can accurately reflect the deep emotional reactions to climate change [19].
Eco-Anxiety Questionnaire (EAQ)	The EAQ seeks to assess individuals' level of eco-anxiety related to environmental concern. It consists of 10 items that assess different aspects of eco-anxiety, such as concern about environmental degradation, emotional distress, and influence on everyday life. Participants rate statements to indicate the degree to which they are concerned and/or uncomfortable about environmental issues using a Likert scale. The EAQ helps discern those notably impacted by environmental stressors, offering a glimpse into the psychological impacts wrought by ecological problems. This well-organized layout enables the accurate assessment and implementation of targeted actions [20].
The Environmental Distress Scale (EDS)	The EDS is used to assess the impact of environmental problems on mental health. It contains 12 items that capture various aspects of emotional distress associated with environmental concerns, such as anxiety, sadness, and hopelessness about the future. It is composed of a Likert scale to indicate the level of concern for the environment. The EDS provides valuable information on how environmental changes and threats affect mental health conditions, helping to identify those who may need additional support and intervention. Its approach is a comprehensive method and helps to understand the broader psychological consequences of environmental problems [21].
The Climate Change and Mental Health Questionnaire (CCMHQ)	The CCMHQ is focused on evaluating the impacts of climate change on individual mental health. It contains 20 items that address a range of mental health conditions associated with climate change, including anxiety, stress, and depression symptoms. Using a Likert scale, subjects reflect on how they feel and what they experience, providing a glimpse into the effects of climate-related stressors on mental health. The CCMHQ helps in identifying and addressing mental health problems caused by climate change and guiding effective interventions [22].
The Climate Change Worry Scale (CCWS)	The CCWS is a tool designed to measure how concerned a person is about climate change. It has 12 items that assess varying facets of climate-related anxiety, such as concerns about environmental degradation and potential future outcomes. On this scale, respondents use a Likert scale to indicate how concerned they are for each item. The CCWS helps to understand the effect of climate change anxiety on mental health and develop personalized interventions for people with high distress levels [23].

Figure 1. A summary of the different factors impacting climate change anxiety.

METHODS

Search strategy

PubMed, Web of Science, Cochrane Library, and Embase databases were used to conduct a comprehensive literature search using the keywords (All Fields: "Climate Change Anxiety") AND (All Fields: "Psychological Impact") as free-text search terms with no time limit. A PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) flow diagram was used to describe the process for study selection (identification, screening, eligibility, inclusion), which is shown in Figure 2 [46]. Titles and abstracts of the database searches were reviewed independently. Full reviews were conducted on all titles and abstracts fulfilling the criteria. Two authors (DL and AC) screened papers. Discrepancies were resolved by a third reviewer (MGM) in case of disagreement. This review has been registered on Open OSF (n): DOI 10.17605/OSF.IO/MWUPN.

PICO evaluations

Using the PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome) model, we constructed our search terms. Its population focused on people living with ecoanxiety. This includes different demographic groups broken down by age and geographic regions. The intervention encompassed all studies examining psychological therapies, community support initiatives, educational programs, and policy reforms designed to mitigate the psychological consequences of climate change. The comparison included treatment versus no treatment, different types of interventions, and the effects of different interventions on different age groups and regions. The primary outcomes were ratings of reduced anxiety, improved overall mental health, and enhanced coping skills. Secondary measures included quality of life, functional limitations, and resilience in years to come.

Inclusion criteria

Studies were included if they reported or investigated the prevalence and psychological effects of CCA and were reported in different age groups and geographical regions. We also included studies that have reported or studied the functional assessment of these patients. This included only papers from human populations published in English that were (i) original or protocol studies, regardless of their methodology, and (ii) epidemiological articles that describe the prevalence and psychological impact of CCA in different age groups and geographic regions.

Exclusion criteria

Studies were excluded from this review if they did not provide data or information on the prevalence and psychological impact of CCA in different age groups and geographic regions. We excluded systematic, integrated, or narrative reviews but reviewed and included reference lists from relevant ones.

Figure 2. PRISMA 2020 flow diagram of evaluated studies.

Quality of included studies: Risk of bias

We assessed the risk of bias in detail with established and well-recognized tools tailored to the study design of the included papers [47–55] to guarantee thorough evaluation of methodological quality. This systematic approach provided a robust framework for identifying potential limitations and inconsistencies, enabling transparent and reliable research methods.

Cochrane risk-of-bias tool for randomized trials (RoB 2)

Of the nine studies, only one was a randomized controlled trial [47]. For this one, we used the updated Cochrane Risk of Bias (RoB 2) tool, which covers five domains: i) bias arising from the randomization process, ii) bias due to deviations from the intended intervention, iii) bias due to missing data on the results, iv) bias in the measurement of the outcome, and v) bias in the selection of the reported result (Figure 3) [56].

Figure 3. Risk of Bias (RoB) of included randomized controlled studies.

Study	Risk of bias domains					Overall
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	
Lindhe et al. 2014	+	-	-	-	-	-

Domains:
 D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.
 D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.
 D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.
 D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.
 D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement
 - Some concerns
 + Low

The risk of bias in non-randomized studies – of interventions (Robins-I)

For the eight non-randomized studies [48-55] we applied the ROBINS-I tool. ROBINS-I assesses bias in seven areas: i) bias due to confounding, ii) bias in participant selection, iii) bias in classification of interventions, iv) bias due to deviations from intended interventions, v) bias due to missing data, vi) bias in outcome measurement, and vii) bias in selection of the reported outcome (Figure 4) [57].

Figure 4. Cochrane Risk of Bias in Non-randomized Studies of Interventions (ROBINS-I).

Study	Risk of bias domains							Overall
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	
Al-Awady et al. 2025	⊗	⊖	⊕	⊖	⊕	⊖	⊕	⊖
Taylor et al. 2008	⊗	⊖	⊕	⊕	⊖	⊗	⊖	⊗
Tsai et al. 2006	⊗	⊗	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊖	⊖	⊗
Gaber et al. 2022	⊖	⊖	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊖	⊕	⊖
Tereshko et al. 2023	⊖	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊖	⊕	⊖
Laterza et al. 2024	⊖	⊖	⊖	⊖	⊖	⊖	⊖	⊖
Bohluli et al. 2011	⊖	⊖	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊖	⊕	⊖
Piovesan et al. 2005	⊖	⊖	⊕	?	⊖	⊖	⊕	⊖
Borodic et al. 2002	⊗	⊖	⊖	⊕	⊕	⊗	⊕	⊗
Alizadeh et al. 2023	⊖	⊖	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊕	⊖

Domains:
D1: Bias due to confounding.
D2: Bias due to selection of participants.
D3: Bias in classification of interventions.
D4: Bias due to deviations from intended interventions.
D5: Bias due to missing data.
D6: Bias in measurement of outcomes.
D7: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement:
⊗ Serious
⊖ Moderate
⊕ Low
? No information

RESULTS

Synthesis of evidence

This systematic review employed a structured approach to evaluate research studies, with the time search conducted within the period of July 15, 2024, to August 10, 2024. Notably, no specific search range was applied to ensure the inclusion of all relevant evidence. In total, 388 articles were found: 97 articles were removed due to duplication after screening; 6 articles were excluded because it was not published in English; 222 articles were excluded based on title and abstract screening. Finally, 54 articles were removed based on screening for inadequate and untraceable study designs (Figure 2). Nine research articles met the inclusion criteria and were therefore included in the review. These studies are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of studies included in the research.

Author	Aim	Study Design/ Intervention	Treatment Period	Sample Size	Outcomes Measures	Main Findings	Study Limitations	Statistical Analyses
Lindhe et al. 2023 [47]	<p>To investigate the effectiveness of a novel iCBT program in reducing psychological distress related to climate change.</p> <p>The focus was on examining its impact on depressive symptoms, stress, quality of life, anxiety, insomnia, climate change-related distress, pro- environmental behavior, and alcohol use.</p>	Randomized Controlled Trial.	Eight weeks.	A total of 60 participants aged between 23 and 73 years.	BDI-II, GAD- 7, PSS.	<p>The treatment group showed moderate to large improvements compared to the wait-list group in depressive symptoms, stress, quality of life, and climate change- related distress. However, there were no significant differences between the groups for anxiety, insomnia, pro- environmental behavior, and alcohol use.</p>	The study's small sample size and pilot nature limit the generalizability of the findings.	<p>Between-group effect sizes were calculated to determine the magnitude of the differences in outcomes between the treatment and wait-list control groups.</p> <p>Moderate to large effect sizes were observed for depressive symptoms, stress, quality of life, and climate change- related distress.</p>

<p>Reyes et al. 2023 [48]</p>	<p>To investigate the relationship between CCA and mental health among Filipinos, particularly focusing on how CCA predicts mental health outcomes.</p>	<p>Predictive Cross-Sectional Study.</p>	<p>The treatment period is not applicable as the study did not involve an intervention but rather assessed participants at a single point in time.</p>	<p>433 Filipinos, including 145 males and 288 females, aged 18 to 26.</p>	<p>CCAS, MHI- 38.</p>	<p>It was found a significant relationship between CCA and mental health, with CCA accounting for 13.5% of the variance in the overall Mental Health Index. Notably, CCA was significantly associated with the Psychological Distress component of the MHI-38 but not with the Psychological Well-being component.</p>	<p>There is a lack of existing research in Environmental Psychology specifically examining the impact of climate change on mental health within the Philippines. Additionally, the investigation of the psychological constructs in this study was limited because it did not take into account other potentially influential variables.</p>	<p>The statistical analyses involved assessing the relationship between CCA and mental health using regression analysis to determine the extent to which CCA predicts mental health outcomes.</p>
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<p>Stewart et al. 2023 [49]</p>	<p>To examine people's concern, worry, and anxiety about the impacts of climate change, and how these emotions relate to psychological distance from climate change and climate-sustainable behaviors.</p>	<p>2 Observational Studies</p>	<p>The treatment period is not applicable as the study did not involve an intervention.</p>	<p>Undergraduate and graduate students.</p>	<p>Qualtrics Survey, CCAS, PDCC.</p>	<p>Study 1: People expressed more worry than anxiety about climate change, especially regarding future generations and societal responses. Anxiety outweighed worry. Study 2: Worry and anxiety about climate change were correlated with psychological distance and predicted climate-sustainable behaviors.</p>	<p>It relied on samples from students at a large state university in the southeastern United States, which may not represent older individuals or those living in different geographic and climatic zones and the measures used depended on self-reported data on concern, worry, and anxiety.</p>	<p>Correlational studies and predictive modeling to examine the relationships between climate change worry, anxiety, psychological distance, and climate-sustainable behaviors.</p>
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Atta et al. 2024 [50]	To examine the relation among climate anxiety, environmental attitude, and job engagement among Nursing University Colleagues from eight different nursing faculties.	Multicenter descriptive, cross-sectional study.	The treatment period is not applicable as the study did not involve an intervention.	359 participants from various regions of Egypt.	CAS, JES	There was no significant influence of demographics on climate anxiety, environmental attitude, and job involvement, but geographical variation were significant.	Study's focus on nursing university colleagues limits the generalizability of its findings to other healthcare professionals or the general population.	The statistical analyses involved examining correlations and assessing the significance of these relationships to understand the impact of climate anxiety on job engagement and environmental attitudes among nursing colleagues.
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Lykins et al. 2024 [51]	To investigate the extent to which CCA contributes to overall antenatal psychological distress and to explore the concerns expectant women have for their existing or future children related to climate change.	Cross-Sectional Study.	The treatment period is not applicable as the study did not involve an intervention.	103 Australian women.	Socio-Demographic Questionnaire, EPDS, CWS, PDS.	CCA significantly accounted for variance in antenatal worry and depression scores. Neither the number of children nor perceived distance to climate change moderated these relationships.	The study focused solely on expectant Australian women, which limit the generalizability of the findings to other populations. Additionally, it did not explore the potential longitudinal impacts of CCA on antenatal distress.	The study used variance analysis to determine the impact of CCA on antenatal worry and depression. Content analysis was applied to qualitative data to identify prevalent themes of concern for participants' children.
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<p>Jones et al. 2023 [52]</p>	<p>To investigate whether patterns of selective attention towards climate-related information and the variability in this attention could explain the inconsistent relationship between eco-anxiety and adaptive pro-environmental behaviors.</p>	<p>Prospective Study.</p>	<p>The treatment period is not applicable as the study did not involve an intervention but rather assessed participants at a single point in time.</p>	<p>130 participants.</p>	<p>HEAS-13, DASS-21.</p>	<p>Eco-anxiety and Attentional bias independently predicted pro-environmental behavior but did not interact directly.</p> <p>However, attentional bias variability moderated the relationship between eco-anxiety and behavior, with higher eco-anxiety predicting greater behavioral engagement only when attentional bias variability was low.</p>	<p>It used an undergraduate sample, which limits the generalizability of the findings and did not test the causal relationship between eco-anxiety and pro-environmental behavior, necessitating experimental manipulations of eco-anxiety to confirm causality.</p>	<p>Moderation analysis to examine the effect of attentional bias variability on the relationship between eco-anxiety and pro-environmental behavior, identifying that attentional bias variability played a significant moderating role.</p>
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Gunsiri et al. [53]	To explore mental health promotion issues related to climate change for young people in Australia.	Exploratory mixed-methods study.	The treatment period is not applicable as the study did not involve an intervention.	60 participants.	Semi-structured interviews.	Negative impacts of climate change on young people's mental health included worry, eco-anxiety, stress, hopelessness, powerlessness, and feeling voiceless. Social media engagement had a dual impact, both positive and negative. Positive impacts of climate action included feelings of optimism and control.	The study's exploratory nature and the small sample size limit the generalizability of the findings.	Data were analyzed thematically and with descriptive statistics to understand the mental health impacts of climate change on young people in Australia.
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<p>Heeren et al. 2022 [54]</p>	<p>To investigate the prevalence and demographic variations of climate anxiety and its associations with pro-environmental behaviors among French-speaking participants from African and European countries.</p>	<p>Cross-Sectional Study.</p>	<p>From May 2021 to July 2021.</p>	<p>2080 French-speaking participants from eight African and European countries.</p>	<p>CAS.</p>	<p>The data showed that 11.64% of participants frequently experienced climate anxiety, highlighting that a significant portion of the population is consistently worried about climate change.</p> <p>Furthermore, 20.72% of these individuals reported that their anxiety had tangible effects on their daily lives, such as difficulties in going to work or socializing. This underscores the real-world impact of climate anxiety, beyond just mental distress.</p>	<p>The limited sample size from African countries precluded definitive conclusions regarding geographic differences.</p>	<p>The study used statistical analyses to assess the prevalence of climate anxiety, demographic differences, and the relationship between climate anxiety and pro-environmental behaviors.</p>
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<p>Thomson et al. 2023 [55]</p>	<p>To replicate previous findings on the relationships among nature connectedness, climate action, climate worry, and mental health, while also exploring the role of climate knowledge.</p> <p>Specifically, it sought to understand these relationships in a geographical context less affected by acute climate events.</p>	<p>Observational Study.</p>	<p>February–April, 2023.</p>	<p>327 adults participants.</p>	<p>CNS, CCAS, CAS,</p>	<p>Nature connectedness was related to climate anxiety, which in turn was associated with psychological distress.</p> <p>Additionally, nature connectedness was linked to both individual and collective climate actions.</p> <p>The relationships varied based on the level of climate knowledge, with the proposed model fitting better for those with high climate knowledge.</p>	<p>The sample was acquired using two different methods—undergraduate students and the general public resulting in a heterogeneous age distribution that might have influenced or obscured some relationships.</p>	<p>The study used survey data analysis to examine the relationships among the variables.</p>
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Note: Climate Change Anxiety (CCA), Climate Change Anxiety Scale (CCAS), Mental Health Inventory (MHI-38), Climate Change Worry Scale (CCWS), Psychological Distance from Climate Change (PDCC), Climate Anxiety Scale (CAS), Job Engagement Scale (JES), Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS), Cambridge Worry Scale (CWS), Psychological Distance Scale (PDS), Hogg Eco-Anxiety Scale (HEAS-13), Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale (DASS-21), Internet-based Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (iCBT), Beck Depression Inventory (BDI-II), Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7-item scale (GAD-7), Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), Connectedness to Nature Scale (CNS).

Advances in Medicine, Psychology and Public Health (AMPPH)

Exploring the psychological impact of climate change anxiety: interventions, reactions, and demographic variations

Existing literature shows the many routes in which climate change impacts mental health, presenting challenges and avenues for intervention. It was conducted as a randomized experimental study to examine the effect of a new online program in cognitive behavioral therapy on climate-change-related mental health problems. Sixty participants were randomly assigned to receive therapist-supported internet-based cognitive behavioral therapy (iCBT) for eight weeks or to a waitlist control group. Compared to the control group, the iCBT group showed significant improvements in depression, stress, quality of life, and climate change-related distress. There were no significant differences in anxiety, insomnia, or alcohol use. Personalized iCBT has been shown to have the benefit of being able to reduce climate change-related mental distress without extinguishing pro-environment behavior [47].

A second paper used predictive cross-sectional analysis to examine the association of CCA with mental health in 433 young Filipinos. CCA explained 13.5% of the variance in the composite Mental Health Index (MHI-38), with robust associations evident. Rather, anxiety about climate change was strongly associated with increased psychological distress, while it did not reveal an association with psychological well-being. These findings highlight the impact of climate change on young adults' mental health in the Philippines through emotional suffering [48]. Based on two other studies, an investigation was undertaken of the experience of emotion in relation to climate change, specifically emotional responses of worry and anxiety. In Study 1, the researchers found that people were more likely to report concern (rather than anxiety) about the impacts of climate change, especially for future generations and to the extent that society would address it.

When anxiety was the primary response, its levels were significantly higher than those of worry. Research 2 found negative relations between psychological distance from climate change and worry and anxiety about climate change. It was found that concern about the climate and psychological distance also played a significant role in predicting climate-sustainable behaviors [49]. Atta et al. explored the relationships of job engagement and climate anxiety with environmental attitude among 359 nursing faculty members in Egypt. Demographic factors had no effect on these variables, but geographical disparities were found to be significant. Climate anxiety was negatively correlated with job engagement and climate attitudes. Heightened climate anxiety was associated with lower environmental attitude and job engagement, while positive environmental attitude was associated with lower job engagement. This study highlights the need for psycho-educational interventions targeted directly toward the nursing profession to mitigate climate-related sadness and increase the mental well-being of nurses [50]. A cross-sectional study of 103 pregnant Australian women assessed the relationship between CCA and antenatal worry and depression. Its findings suggested that fear around climate was a bigger driver of worry and depression during pregnancy than either the number of children people had or a perceived distance to climate change.

Qualitative data describe significant health concerns among children, including illness, extreme weather, and food/water safety [51]. Meanwhile, Jones and colleagues explored how eco-anxiety relates to pro-environmental behavior, people's actions to minimize harm to the environment, with a particular focus on how orienting oneself toward climate-related information could impact the relationship between eco-anxiety and pro-environmental action. They found that eco-anxiety and attentional bias separately predicted pro-environmental behavior (in a dot-probe task), with no interaction between the 2 variables. However, for participants who exhibited low variability of attentional bias, greater eco-anxiety was related to more engagement in pro-environmental behaviors. This could suggest that frequent degrees of exposure to climate information could enhance the adaptability of eco-anxiety, which offers a more strategic use of this emotional response to address the climate crisis [52]. Using interviews and surveys, an investigative mixed-methods study among Australians aged 18-24 explores the effects of climate change on mental health. The findings showed that climate change had an adverse impact on mental well-being, leading to apprehension, eco-anxiety, stress, despair, and hopelessness, and

that social media had a double-edged influence in this regard. Actions that one can take to address climate change can lead to positive mental health effects, such as a sense of hope and empowerment.

These findings highlight the importance of public health efforts to educate youths on the mental health impacts of climate change and to promote engagement in climate action and nature-based activities [53]. Heeren et al. studied how climate anxiety influences the everyday behaviors and environmental practices of a sample of 2080 French-speaking individuals from Africa and Europe. 11.64% reported having regular climate anxiety, and 20.72% said it affected their daily life. Women and younger people faced greater climate anxiety, and there were no significant differences among different locations. Though climate anxiety was associated with eco-friendly behaviors, this association was weaker among those who experienced climate anxiety frequently. These findings inform us that climate anxiety can become a barrier to daily functions and adaptation [54]. A final study replicated previous work on the relationships between nature connectedness, climate anxiety, and psychological distress in a different geographical context with lower levels of directly experienced climate events.

The study of 327 adults confirmed that being connected to nature was associated with climate anxiety and psychological distress. There was also an association found between nature connectedness and both individual and collective climate action, but the association with psychological distress was more complex. The model worked better for individuals with greater knowledge of climate change, confirming that such knowledge affects the relations of these variables [55]. A recently published experimental study demonstrated the effectiveness of an Internet-based cognitive behavioral therapy (iCBT) program addressing mental health issues associated with climate change. In the iCBT group, significant improvements in depression, stress, and climate-related distress were observed over eight weeks compared with those on a waiting list. Yet, no meaningful changes were observed in anxiety, insomnia, or alcohol consumption.

These results suggest that targeted iCBT interventions will be important in managing distress and enabling individuals to maintain their pro-environmental behaviors. Other research has focused on the emotional costs of climate change on young people. For instance, a study conducted among 433 young Filipinos found climate change anxiety was significantly associated with psychological distress, explaining 13.5% of the variation in their mental health index. Though worries about climate change heightened emotional distress, they appeared not to have a significant effect on overall psychological well-being. This follows the nuanced sites at which climate issues touch mental well-being, particularly for at-risk communities. Another recognized important factor in understanding climate change, how “close” people feel to its devastating effects, is psychological distance.

This distance impacts both concern and anxiety around climate change, research has shown. Excitingly, in many different iterations, worry often takes precedence over anxiety regarding their concern over issues for future generations and the response of society towards the crisis. Those feelings, in turn, play an important role in fueling pro-environmental actions, showing the complex ways that feelings and behaviors related to the climate crisis are interrelated. Some populations appear particularly susceptible to the mental health effects of climate change. For example, pregnant women in Australia have reported that concerns about climate change increased anxiety and depressive symptoms, especially about how to protect children from health threats going forward, extreme weather, and having food or water. Tested in young Australian adults aged 18 to 24, the results suggested similarly high levels of eco-anxiety, often associated with stress, despair, and hopelessness. Social media reportedly had the opposite effect, increasing negative feelings and decreasing positive ones, while climate action increased a sense of hopefulness and empowerment.

Research has also examined the impact of ecoanxiety on behavior. It was found that increased anxiety around climate change does encourage increased green behaviors, at least in people exposed to climate content again and again. But extreme eco-anxiety can interfere with everyday functioning, showing how important it is to find ways to redirect this feeling constructively and to temper its adverse effects. Collectively, these findings highlight the broad and complex influence of

climate change on psychological health across diverse populations and environments. Commentaries in this collection discuss the advantages of developing intervention strategies, health programs, and school curricula designed to address these dual yet interconnected challenges of mental health and ecosystem preservation.

DISCUSSION

This systematic review assesses the prevalence and psychological impact of CCA across study populations, age groups, and geographic regions. These studies show that climate change has a complex impact on mental health and that the impacts vary widely. Results from experiments indicate that iCBT is effective at reducing climate change-related distress, depression, and stress, suggesting that targeted interventions may mitigate some of the psychological impacts of climate change and promote pro-environmental behaviors [47]. In contrast, CCA was found to significantly increase psychological distress in young adults in the Philippines and in pregnant women in Australia, representing a strong emotional burden that may exacerbate concerns and affect depression status [48,49,51]. Additional analyses demonstrated that CCA can reduce job involvement and green beliefs, in particular, with regard to the nursing profession, implying that an increase in anxiety may limit both work and personal environmental commitment [50]. Moreover, both relationships between eco-anxiety and a high concern towards climate issues were positively related to more aspects of pro-environmental actions, suggesting that eco-anxiety may be utilized as a tool for positively modifying behavior [52]. Indeed, research revealed that climate anxiety interferes with everyday functioning and adjustment [51,55]. However, nature connection can mitigate climate anxiety [53] and influence climate action and efforts [54]. This aspect further supports the need for public health intervention towards emotional reactions to climate change since the mental health impacts of climate change are significant [52].

In a study conducted by Lindhe et al. [58], it was discovered that individuals receiving iCBT for climate change-related distress felt emotional relief, developed better coping strategies, and felt empowered after completing the therapy [58]. Komariah et al. [59] found that iCBT was very effective in decreasing depression and anxiety symptoms amid the COVID-19 outbreak, indicating its potential to handle emergency scenarios such as climate change [59]. DaPonte et al. [60] discovered that iCBT is successful in addressing anxiety and depression, and participants valued its ease of use and ability to maintain privacy [60]. In their study, Oliveira et al. [61] demonstrated that iCBT can help reduce anxiety symptoms in college students, who frequently face difficulties in obtaining conventional mental health care [61]. These findings suggest the promise of iCBT in providing the comprehensive support needed by individuals living with climate change anxiety (CCA), especially for those who do not have easy access to traditional therapy. A series of studies has confirmed the complexity of the relationship between eco-anxiety and ecological behavior, showing how concerns about climate change influence daily decisions and mental health. The relationship between eco-anxiety and environmental attitudes was studied by Lutz et al. [62], who found that eco-anxiety can negatively impact health while also motivating individuals to adopt environmentally friendly behaviors [62].

In the study by Pavani et al. [63], it was discovered that eco-anxiety emotions can lead people to participate in environmental initiatives, even when they experience adverse emotions [63]. The study by Shao and Yu revealed a complex relationship between anxiety and action, showing that media coverage can increase eco-anxiety and promote advocacy for ecological behaviors [63]. Meanwhile, Mathers-Jones and Todd explored the effects of attention on the impact of eco-anxiety on pro-environmental behavior, based on the idea that talking about climate change can fuel eco-anxiety and motivate pro-environmental actions [65]. The study by Ballman et al. also mentioned that environmental anxiety can make people more likely to adopt green behaviors [66]. More recent works have explored emotional pathways and reactions and how they influence political actions and attitudes towards climate change. For example, Davidson and Kecinski [67] studied how emotions such as fear, anger, and hope influence individuals' responses to climate change, emphasizing their strong impact on people's attitudes towards climate-related policies and individual behaviors [67]. Myers et al. [68] studied the impact of emotional reactions to climate change information on policy support. The study found that emotions such

as fear and anger have significant effects on support for such policies, suggesting that engaging public emotions is the most effective way to address public support for climate action [68]. Students may also react emotionally to climate change education. Jones and Whitehouse [69] describe how students often felt emotional, expressing anger and frustration, during and after exposure to climate change education. Although challenging, these emotions can motivate students to engage in environmental activism and help shape the future [69].

Schneider et al. [70] focused on the effects of positive emotions on climate change. In their study, evidence suggested that feelings such as optimism and satisfaction can strengthen motivation to participate in sustainable actions, and these moments help counterbalance the generally pessimistic tone of climate change discussions [70]. In a study by Böhm et al. [71–74], emotional responses to climate change were examined in France, Germany, Norway, and the United Kingdom. They found that while fear and concern were widespread, there were striking differences in emotional responses between countries that explained both public support for climate policies and individual behaviors [71]. On the other hand, researchers have increasingly studied the interplay between these factors, specifically in connection with CCA and the concept of nature connectedness, its influences on mental health, and behavior.

Research has shown that feeling close to nature has been able to lower feelings of climate-change anxiety, as well as improve mental health. For instance, a strong connection to nature may help reduce climate anxiety, as Matera et al. study [72] attests, and environmental attachment may provide psychological benefits [72]. Curll et al. [73] supported this perspective, showing that increasing nature connectedness can provide motivation to work on climate change and improve mental health. Nonetheless, the buffering effect of nature connectedness on climate concern may be lessened when experiencing different forms of stress and worry [73]. Wullenkord et al. [74] found that while connection to nature can be a resilience factor, it is less effective under multiple stressors, suggesting that nature alone may not fully protect from climate anxiety in addition to other stressors [74].

Furthermore, Kenstler and Shelley [75] noted that environmental science students displayed high levels of eco-anxiety and connection to nature, with no demonstrated increase in resilience. Media coverage and nature connectedness are important contributing factors to eco-anxiety [75]. Jalin et al. [76] found that media exposure, along with connectedness to nature, plays a role in eco-anxiety, while Reese et al. [77] identified that the perception of climate-related dangers is a major predictor of climate-induced anxiety [76,77]. Furthermore, climate anxiety and feeling connected to nature can influence sustainable consumer behaviors, leading to a positive impact on intentions to stay at eco-resorts. Shimul et al. [78] demonstrated that these factors positively influence consumers' intentions to choose eco-friendly accommodations [78]. These studies exemplify the intricate features that climate anxiety may possess, its relations to feelings about nature, emotional responses, and pro-environmental behaviors. While interventions like iCBT and a strong connection with nature can significantly alleviate climate anxiety, they do not come without their challenges, especially in periods of extreme stress. Therefore, further research and targeted strategies are necessary to adequately address both the mental health consequences and support a sustainable behavior [79].

Mapping the research landscape of climate change anxiety: A geographical perspective

The assortment of research featured in this review provides an initial worldwide outlook on CCA, with studies carried out in Europe (Sweden, France, Belgium), Asia (Philippines, Egypt), North America (United States, Canada), and Oceania (Australia). This distribution provides preliminary insights into the ways CCA appear across various cultural and environmental settings. Nonetheless, considerable geographical disparities still exist. Significantly, there is a lack of data from Africa, with merely one study performed in Egypt and an absence of representation from South America and extensive areas of Asia, encompassing densely populated and climate-sensitive regions. The lack of studies in these fields restricts the applicability of the existing results and underscores the necessity for additional exploration in varied international contexts to comprehend the subtle effects of climate change on mental health among diverse groups and cultures. Although the

studies included offer useful individual insights, making direct comparisons across countries is laden with difficulties. Methodological diversity is a crucial element, as studies utilize distinct scales to assess climate anxiety (e.g., Climate Change Anxiety Scale, modified Hogg Eco-Anxiety Scale), various mental health outcome metrics (e.g., Beck Depression Inventory, Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7, Mental Health Inventory), and differing research designs (e.g., randomized controlled trial, cross-sectional, prospective). For example, the iCBT intervention research in Sweden [47] cannot be directly compared to the cross-sectional study regarding Filipino youth [48] that concentrated on the correlations between CCA and mental health.

Additionally, the particular emphasis of the research differs; certain studies investigate the effect of CCA on job engagement [50], whereas others analyze its correlation with pro-environmental behavior [52] or antenatal distress [51]. These methodological variations complicate the ability to reach conclusive insights regarding cross-national differences in the occurrence and effects of CCA. The nations covered in this review encounter climate change differently, potentially affecting the psychological reactions of their citizens. For instance, the Philippines, a group of islands in Southeast Asia, is particularly susceptible to severe weather occurrences like typhoons and faces direct risks from rising sea levels, which may increase stress linked to real and urgent climate effects [48]. Conversely, Sweden, though facing climate change impacts like shifted seasons and rising temperatures, may have a distinct view on urgency and danger, potentially affecting the character and intensity of CCA [47]. Likewise, Australia has experienced extreme climate-related incidents such as bushfires and droughts, which likely account for the considerable scientific focus and numerous studies on CCA carried out in this area [51-53].

The degree of scientific focus on CCA within a particular nation may be shaped by elements like government research funding priorities, the recognized effects of climate change on public welfare [54-63] and the involvement of local research organizations in this developing area. Somewhat restricted research from specific areas may indicate a diminished emphasis on mental health concerning climate change or insufficient resources allocated for those studies [64-68].

Future directions

This review highlights the necessity for research on CCA to be more geographically diverse. Future research should focus on exploring overlooked areas to offer a broader global perspective. Utilizing more standardized methods and outcome metrics would enable cross-cultural comparisons and permit a deeper understanding of how CCA appears and affects individuals in various settings. Moreover, studies might examine how localized climate change effects, cultural influences, and socio-economic factors affect the experience of CCA and shape resilience strategies and coping mechanisms. Exploring the influence of national policies and public health strategies in tackling CCA in various countries would be an important direction for future studies.

Limitations

This systematic review analyzes CCA, differing in populations, age ranges, and geographical areas. Its range of studies offers an all-around view of the impact of climate change on mental health and possible solutions. Employing various methodologies like experimental, cross-sectional, and mixed methods, the analysis differs greatly in its data, which makes it more reliable and comprehensive in its findings. Besides, by highlighting new trends like the impact of eco-anxiety on sustainable behaviors and the importance of nature connection, the review is current and topical. Another advantage is the inclusion of bias risk assessment for the chosen assessments to provide higher accuracy and reliability of the findings. There are some limitations, though, which should be noted. Focusing on English-language publications and peer-reviewed papers may introduce bias in study inclusion, limiting heterogeneity of research examined and potentially influencing generalizability of findings. The variations in CCA definitions and measurements between studies make it difficult to synthesize findings and reach uniform conclusions. In addition, although interventions such as iCBT have been found to be effective, their success can be influenced by the individual and context factors that may not always be comprehensively included within the review.

The evaluation is mostly focused on short-term outcomes and the short-term effects, leading to a limited understanding of the long-term consequences of CCA as well as the intervention benefits. One of the limitations is a narrow focus on papers covered and reviewed and for which selection was made for review, highlighting a need for more work to delve deeper into the topic of this theme. In the end, while studies in different regions had been included, the review cannot necessarily capture cultural differences that could affect CCA effectiveness and intervention results.

CONCLUSIONS

The systematic review provides an in-depth examination of CCA, its multifaceted impacts on mental health, and the complex responses from various populations and regions. The evidence highlights that fear of climate change is a major cause of psychological distress, resulting in extreme levels of depression, stress, and hopelessness, particularly among youths and people residing in climate-risk-prone areas [69-71]. This stress inhibits normal functioning and impacts behavior, leading people to resort to environmental activism as a coping mechanism. While it may be emancipating, this is usually accompanied by burnout if not properly managed.

The article highlights that interventions like iCBT are able to minimize stress caused by climate change, improve coping, and promote green behavior. Still, there are barriers to overcome, such as managing differential anxiety and response levels within different age groups and geographical locations, beyond ensuring sensitivity to attitudes towards mental illness in a culturally diverse population. The next piece of work should focus on targeting the application of longitudinal designs for estimating the long-term outcomes of CCA and interventions' effectiveness. A review of how various coping behaviors function under many different socio-economic and cultural situations is equally important. Moreover, integrating climate change concerns within general mental health systems and facilitating public participation in environmental mental health can help ensure the effectiveness of interventions.

Examining the nexus between eco-anxiety, nature contact, and sustainability can give critical information for mitigating climate anxiety and facilitating healthy environmental behaviors [72-80]. Management of CCA typically uses a number of strategies that include emotional support, community connectedness, and delivering preventive education to foster resilience and well-being in the face of environmental adversity.

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